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POTENTIALLY HARMFUL EXCIPIENTS IN PEDIATRIC ORAL COUGH MEDICINES AUTHORIZED IN SERBIA

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Some pharmaceutical excipients may cause adverse effects or excipient-related contraindications and interactions. The aim of this study was to identify all excipients with known effect (EKE) in pediatric oral cough medicines authorized in Serbia and evaluate EKE labeling in the corresponding Summaries of product characteristics (SmPCs) and Package leaflets (PLs). The study was designed as a post-authorization safety study and safety of excipients was considered in accordance with recommendations of the European Medicines Agency. Out of a total of 64 oral cough medicines authorized in Serbia, 58 (90.63%) of them were approved for pediatric use and all of these pediatric medicines contained one or more EKE. A total of 27 different EKE were identified, from 6 different functional categories (sweeteners, preservatives/antioxidants, electrolytes, solvents, solubilizing/emulsifying agents, and coloring agents) with most of them present in products approved for use across all ages of children and adolescents above the age of 2. A significant number of EKE labeling deficiencies were detected in product PLs and SmPCs, including complete omission of one or more EKE for 74.14% of products, as well as missing or incomplete EKE quantitative (44.83% of products) and/or safety information (44.83% of products). As negative effects of excipients may be more pronounced in the pediatric population compared to adults, it is especially important to consider EKE related safety issues when prescribing and dispensing medicines intended for children. Revision of the product PLs and SmPCs is recommended in order to eliminate deficiencies and improve EKE labeling.

Keywords: Pediatrics, Pharmaceutical Adjuvants, Pharmacovigilance, Risk Assessment.

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